

FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF REGIONAL RURAL BANKS IN INDIA

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Abstract

The study was undertaken to measure the financial performance of regional rural banks in India from 2001-2020. The methodology used to study the financial performances of Regional Rural Banks in India was ANOVA. The study conducted was descriptive in nature and data was collected from published annual reports of RBI and NABARD for the period 2001-2020. Results revealed that the deposits of RRBs increased from Rs. 44,539.15 crores in the year 2001-02 to Rs. 5,25,226 crores in the year 2020-21 registering the growth rate 9.71 per cent. The amount of loans/advances given by all the RRBs in country increased from Rs. 18,629.55 crores in 2001-02 to Rs. 3,15,181 crores in 2020-21 registering the growth of 18.56 per cent. CD ratio increased from 41.83 per cent in the year 2001-02 to 64 per cent in 2020-21. There has been consistent growth in the sphere of credit deposit ratio. The amount of borrowed funds increased from Rs. 4,524 crores in 2001-02 to Rs. 67,864 crores in the year 2020-21 and the owned funds increased from Rs. 4,059 crores in 2001-02 to Rs. 31,629 crores in 2020-21. The net profit position of RRBs raised from Rs. 600.62 crores in 2001-02 to Rs. 1,682 crores in 2020-21 indicating that RRBs are operating on profitable line.

Keywords: Financial performance, credit deposit ratio, borrowed fund, owned fund)

Introduction:

Agriculture and rural development are vital to the growth of the Indian economy; hence regional rural banks are crucial. With their extensive network, RRBs have a greater reach into India's rural garden. Rural credit's performance is heavily reliant on their financial strength and competence. Regional rural banks are the main financing organisations in rural regions, and they are in charge of meeting the credit needs of many different types of farm credit. Overdrafts, loan collection, and non-performing assets are all key issues that regional rural banks are dealing with these days. As a result, it is necessary to investigate the financial performance of India's regional rural banks. The research relies on secondary data gathered from annual reports. The RRBs were 50 per cent, 15 per cent, and 35 per cent owned by the federal government, state government, and sponsoring bank, respectively. Growth in the number of branches and district coverage, Geographical coverage, Branch and staff productivity, Capital funds, Loans outstanding and investments made, Deposit mobilisation, Recovery performance, and Non-performing assets are among the measures used to evaluate RRB performance.

Following independence, the Indian government's main goal was to improve credit policy in the country (particularly in rural areas) and expand institutional financing in order to reduce the role of non-institutional credit sources such as money lenders, traders, landlords, commission agents, credit from relatives, and so on. Cooperative banks were seen as a viable solution to the problem of rural financing by the All India Rural Credit Survey Committee (AIRCS) in 1951. State governments and the Reserve Bank of India backed cooperative

banks at various levels. Much was expected of cooperative banks, but due to a lack of financial resources, they were unable to provide the credit needs of the rural sector in accordance with the needs of farmer's movements. (Satish. *et al.*, 2017)

The research is important for evaluating the financial performance of India's Regional Rural Banks. The outcomes of this study will aid policymakers in their efforts to improve the RRBs' operational effectiveness in India. Data on changes in the performance of RRBs in India during the pre-decade and post-decade periods were collected. The study would run from 2001 through 2020.

Methodology:

The study was based on secondary data collected for 20 years from 2001-02 to 2020-21, various sources using appropriate analytical techniques to satisfy the objective.

Analysis of Variance ANOVA)**Definition of ANOVA:**

The analysis of variance is the systematic algebraic procedure of decomposing (i.e. partitioning) overall variation (i.e. total variation) in the responses observed in an experiment into different component of variations such as treatment variation and error variation. Each component is attributed identifiable cause or source of variation. It is used to measure the financial performance of RRBs in India from 2001-2020.

Formula of one-way ANOVA

Numerically, one-way ANOVA is a generalisation of the two-sample t test. The F statistic compares the variability between the groups to the variability within the groups

$$F = \frac{MST}{MSE}$$

$$MST = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{T_i^2}{n_i} \right) - \frac{G^2}{n}}{k - 1}$$

$$MSE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} Y_{ij}^2 - \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{T_i^2}{n_i} \right)}{n - k}$$

Where,

F- Statistics for variance ratio,

MST - is the mean square due to treatments/groups (between groups),

MSE - is the mean square due to error (within groups, residual mean square), Y_{ij} - is an observation,

T_i - is a group total,

G - is the grand total of all observations,

n_i - is the number in i th group and n is the total number of observations.

Table 1 Deposits Mobilized and Lending Operations Of RRBs (Rs. In Crore)

Years	Deposits Rs. In Crore)	Increment In Deposits	% Increment In Deposits	Loans/Advances (Rs. In Crore)	Increment In Loans/ Advances	% Increment In Loans/Advances	Credit Deposit Ratio
2000-2001	38,277.78	-	-	15,815.80	-	-	41.32
2001-2002	44,539.15	6,261.37	16.36	18,629.55	2,813.75	17.79	41.83
2002-2003	50,098.00	5,558.85	12.48	22,158.00	3,528.45	18.94	44.23
2003-2004	56,350.00	6,252.00	12.48	26,113.00	3,955.00	17.85	46.34
2004-2005	62,143.00	5,793.00	10.28	32,870.03	6,757.03	25.88	52.89
2005-2006	71,328.83	9,185.83	14.78	39,712.57	6,842.54	20.82	55.68
2006-2007	83,143.55	11,814.72	16.56	48,492.59	8,780.02	22.11	58.32
2007-2008	99,093.46	15,949.91	19.18	58,984.27	10,491.68	21.64	59.52
2008-2009	1,20,189.90	21,096.44	21.29	67,802.10	8,817.83	14.95	56.41
2009-2010	1,45,034.95	24,845.05	20.67	82,819.10	15,017.00	22.15	57.1
2010-2011	1,66,232.34	21,197.39	14.62	98,917.43	16,098.33	19.44	59.51
2011-2012	1,86,336.07	20,103.73	12.09	1,16,384.97	17,467.54	17.66	62.46
2012-2013	2,11,488.00	25,151.93	13.5	1,37,078.00	20,693.03	17.78	64.82
2013-2014	2,39,494.00	28,006.00	13.24	1,59,406.00	22,328.00	16.29	66.56
2014-2015	2,73,018.00	33,524.00	14	1,80,955.00	21,549.00	13.52	66.28
2015-2016	3,15,048.00	42,030.00	15.39	2,07,279.00	26,324.00	14.55	65.79
2016-2017	3,71,910.00	56,862.00	18.04	2,26,175.00	18,896.00	9.11	60.81
2017-2018	4,00,459.00	28,549.00	7.69	2,53,978.00	27,803.00	12.29	63.42
2018-2019	4,34,444.00	33,985.00	8.48	2,61,953.00	7,975.00	3.14	65.00
2019-2020	4,78,737.00	44,293.00	10.19	2,86,919.00	24,966.00	9.53	62.00
2020-2021	5,25,226.00	46489.00	9.71	3,15,181.00	53,262.00	18.56	64.00

Results and Discussion:

The financial performance of regional rural banks in India from 2001-2020

Deposits Mobilized and Lending Operations of RRBs

RRB is showing considerable improvement in their lending and deposit performance. The deposit mobilized increased over the period was 11.79 times and lending was 16.91 times and the CD ratio increased to 64% up to 2020-21.

Deposits: Deposit Mobilization is a part of banking services and one of the essential jobs of RRBs. Non-stop and sufficient amount of deposit mobilization will ensure the banks to operate their function of

lending and investment on which the success of the bank depends. Being an essential job the table 2 shows that the deposits of RRBs increased from Rs. 44,539.15 crore in the year 2001-02 to Rs. 5,25,226 crore in the year 2020-21 registering the growth rate 9.71%. Loans/Advances: The main motive behind the birth of RRBs is to improve the credit conditions in rural areas and to develop rural economy by providing credit and other banking facilities to the rural population. It is shown in the table 2 that the advances and loans given by all the RRBs in country increased from Rs. 18,629.55 crore in 2001-02 to Rs. 3,15,181 crore in 2020-21 registering the growth of 18.56%.

Credit Deposit Ratio (C/D Ratio): The genesis of RRBs taken place to develop rural economy by providing credit and other banking facilities for the development of agriculture, trade and other productive activities in the rural areas. The credit deposit ratio of the bank indicates the creation of credit out of the deposits mobilized by

the banks which has been furnished in Table-2. The table exhibits that CD ratio increased from 41.83% in the year 2001-02 to 64% in 2020-21. There has been consistent growth in the sphere of credit deposit ratio. The year 2013-14 registered a higher rate i.e., 66.56%.

Years	Credit Deposit Ratio
2000-01	41.32
2001-02	41.83
2002-03	44.23
2003-04	46.34
2004-05	52.89
2005-06	55.68
2006-07	58.32
2007-08	59.52
2008-09	56.41
2009-10	57.1
2010-11	59.51
2011-12	62.46
2012-13	64.82
2013-14	66.56
2014-15	66.28
2015-16	65.79
2016-17	60.81
2017-18	63.42
2018-19	65.00
2019-20	62.00
2020-2021	64.00

Source: Annual Reports of NABARD

The ANOVA test was performed to compare the performance of deposit mobilization with loans/advances of RRBs, in order to know whether there is improvement of performance of these banks in post-decade over pre-decade. From the ANOVA test results it was observed that the F-statistics found Significant, which reveals that performance of loans/advances differs significantly with deposits of the RRBs.

Capital Composition

In comparison to cooperative banks and commercial banks, RRBs plays a vital role in the rural credit market of India. The motive behind the establishment of the RRB was to mobilize deposits, access to central money market and modernized outlook. Sound financial

position is very essential for any organization to render the services to the society constantly. The total capital of RRBs is divided in to two types of capital i.e., (A) Owned Capital and (B) Borrowed Capital.

Table 3 revealed that the year-wise growth in total capital i.e. growth in owned funds and borrowed funds of RRBs in India. Both the owned funds and borrowed funds have constantly been increased over the period of 2001-2020. The figure of borrowed funds increased from Rs. 4,524 crores in 2001-02 to Rs. 67,864 crores in the year 2020-21 and the owned funds increased from Rs. 4,059 crores in 2001-02 to Rs. 31,629 crores in 2020-21.

Year	Owned Funds	Growth %	% to Total Funds	Borrowed Funds	Growth %	% to Funds	Total Funds
2001-02	4,059.00	-	47.29	4,524.00	-	52.71	8583.00
2002-03	4,666.00	14.95	49.3	4,799.00	6.08	50.7	9465.00
2003-04	5,438.00	16.55	54.2	4,595.00	-4.25	45.8	10033.00
2004-05	6181.27	13.67	52.81	5524.32	20.22	47.19	11705.59
2005-06	6646.59	7.53	47.65	7302.59	32.19	52.35	13949.18

2006-07	7285.97	9.62	42.7	9775.8	33.87	57.3	17061.77
2007-08	8732.59	19.85	43.17	11494	17.58	56.83	20226.59
2008-09	10910.29	24.94	46.14	12734.65	10.79	53.86	23644.94
2009-10	12247.16	12.25	39.49	18770.06	47.39	60.51	31017.22
2010-11	13838.92	13	34.31	26490.8	41.13	65.69	40329.72
2011-12	16462.00	18.95	35.21	30288.84	14.34	64.79	46750.84
2012-13	19445.00	18.12	33.81	38073.00	25.7	66.19	57518.00
2013-14	22172.00	14.02	30.62	50230.00	31.93	69.38	72402.00
2014-15	25084.00	13.13	29.68	59422.00	18.3	70.32	84506.00
2015-16	27716.00	10.49	36.55	48110.00	19.04	63.45	75826.00
2016-17	28333.00	2.22	35.45	51588.00	7.22	64.54	79921.00
2017-18	29653.00	4.65	33.96	57647.00	11.74	66.03	87300.00
2018-19	29232.00	1.42	35.31	53548.00	7.65	64.68	82780.00
2019-20	28195.00	3.54	34.13	54393.00	1.57	65.86	82588.00

Source: Annual Reports of NABARD

The owned funds and borrowed funds of RRBs were compared using ANOVA and “t” test is performed to analyse the changes in total funds of pre-decade period with post-decade period, to test whether the pre-decade and post decade period process has resulted in improving the total funds’ performance of these banks in India during 2001-2020.

The ANOVA test result shows that the value of F-Statistics found Significant which reveals performance of owned funds differs significantly with borrowed funds of the RRBs.

1.3 Profit Position of RRBs in India:

In a highly competitive environment RRBs needed considerable amount of profit for their survival and growth. RRBs are primary component and backbone of financial system. Hence, it is crucial to earn profits by RRBs to build the strong financial system. Earning sufficient Profits is a sign of fruitful utilization of bank funds and reveals the operative efficiency of banks. Higher the amount of profit greater the operating efficiency and vice versa. The information relating to profitability of RRBs is given in Table 4.

Table 4 illustrates that the net profit position of RRBs raised from Rs. 600.62 crore in 2001-02 to Rs. 1,682 crores in 2020-21 indicating that RRBs are operating on profitable line. It is also understandable from the table that due to the process of amalgamation RRBs improve the net profit position year after year. It is also clear that the number of loss making RRBs have reduced from 26 in 2001-02 to 13 in 2020-21 this count was Zero in the year 2013-14 and the amount of loss declined from Rs. 75.86 crore in 2001-02 to Rs. 0 in 2013-14, but in last seven years the 19 RRBs have suffered a more loss of 4411 crores in the year 2019-20. The accumulated loss making RRBs have increased to 17 and amount of accumulated loss also increased to Rs. 8264 crores in 2020-21.

The amount of profit and amount of loss of the RRBs were compared using ANOVA, to test whether the amount of profit has improved in comparison to the amount of loss of RRBs in India during 2001-2020.

In pre-decade period the gross NPA in percentage is declining from 18.84 per cent in 2001 to 3.72 per cent in 2010. An increment can be seen from 6.15 per cent in 2015 to 6.45 per cent in 2016 (as per unaudited data). Gross non-performing assets are percentage of total loans outstanding witnessed a gradual increase from 3.75 per cent as in 2011 to 10.43 per cent as in the year 2020. The asset quality deterioration moderated as on 31 March 2020 mainly on account of moratorium granted by RBI under the COVID-19 Regulatory package resulting in asset classification stand still during the moratorium period. As on 31 March 2020, the GNPA per cent under priority stood at 10.8 per cent and the GNPA under non-priority sector portfolio stood at 6.5 per cent.

Conclusion:

The deposits of RRBs increased from Rs. 44,539.15 crores in the year 2001-02 to Rs. 5,25,226 crores in the year 2020-21 registering the growth rate 9.71 per cent.

The amount of loans/advances given by all the RRBs in country increased from Rs. 18,629.55 crores in 2001-02 to Rs. 3,15,181 crores in 2020-21 registering the growth of 18.56 per cent.

CD ratio increased from 41.83 per cent in the year 2001-02 to 64 per cent in 2020-21. There has been consistent growth in the sphere of credit deposit ratio.

The increment in percentage of total business took place because deposits and lending operations registered the growth of 9.71 per cent and 18.56 per cent respectively in the year 2020-2021.

The net profit of RRBs raised from Rs. 600.62 crore in 2001-02 to Rs. 1,682 crores in 2020-21 indicating that RRBs are operating on profitable line.

The gross NPA of all RRBs decreased constantly in percentage, the gross NPA increased from Rs. 2,980 crores in 2001 to Rs. 31,381 crores in 2021.

Year	No. of RRBs	RRBs in profit	Amount of profit	RRBs in loss	Amount of loss	Net Profit	RRBs accumulated losses with	Accumulated losses
2001-02	196	170	676.48	26	75.86	600.62	NA	2,792.59
2002-03	196	167	699.93	29	92.05	607.88	NA	2,694.06
2003-04	196	156	733.97	40	214.68	519.29	90	2,752.25
2004-05	196	166	902.6	30	154.49	748.11	83	2,715.01
2005-06	133	111	807.79	22	190.66	617.13	58	2,636.85
2006-07	96	81	926.4	15	301.25	625.15	39	2,759.49
2007-08	91	82	1,383.69	8	55.58	1,328.11	36	2,624.22
2008-09	86	80	1,823.55	6	35.91	1,787.64	31	2,299.98
2009-10	82	79	2,514.83	3	5.65	2,509.18	27	1,775.06
2010-11	82	75	2,420.75	7	71.32	2,349.43	23	1,532.39
2011-12	82	79	1,886.15	3	28.87	1,857.28	22	1,332.57
2012-13	64	63	2,275.00	1	2.07	2,272.93	11	1,091.00
2013-14	57	57	2,694.00	0	0	2,694.00	8	948.00
2014-15	56	51	2,921.00	5	176	2,745.00	8	1,072.00
2015-16	56	50	2,206.00	6	188	2,018.00	8	1,050.00
2016-17	56	49	2,604.00	7	387	2,218.00	8	1,147.00
2017-18	56	45	2,530.00	11	1005	1,525.00	8	1,866.00
2018-19	53	39	1759	14	2411	-652	11	2,887.00
2019-20	45	26	2,203.00	19	4411	-2208	17	6,467.00
2020-21	43	30	3550	13	1867	1682	17	8264.00

Source: Annual Reports of NABARD

Policy Implications

The following are some suggestions for policymakers of the banking sector for further decision-making process.

The RRB must strengthen effective credit administration by way

- of credit appraisal, monitoring the progress of loans and their efficient recovery.
- The credit policy of the RRB should be based on the group approach of financing rural activities.

Table 5: Percentage of Gross NPA to loans of RRBs in India (Rs. In Crore)

Years	Gross Loans	Gross NPAs	per cent to Total
June-01	15815.8	2980	18.84
June-02	18629.55	3065	16.45
June-03	22158.00	3200	14.44
June-04	26113.00	3298	12.63
June-05	32870.03	2804	8.53
June-06	39712.57	2891	7.28
June-07	48492.59	3176	6.55
June-08	58984.27	3569	6.05
June-09	67802.92	2807	4.14
June-10	82819.10	3081	3.72
June-11	98917.43	3709	3.75
June-12	116384.97	5854	5.03
June-13	137078.00	8362	6.1
June-14	159406.00	9708	6.09

June-15	180955.00	11129	6.15
June-16	207279.00	13369	6.45
June-17	226175.00	18255	8.07
June-18	253978.00	24059	9.47
June-19	280755.00	30317	10.8
June-20	298256.00	31106	10.43

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